

Towards Modelling Energy Demand of Vehicles in Cities: An Agent-Based Method

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Summary

In 2020, over 3 million electric vehicles (EVs) and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEV) were sold, a 40% increase from 2019. There are now over 10 million electric cars on the roads globally, and this number is expected to rise to 300 million by 2030. Due to the significant environmental and health implications of internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs), national governments are adopting cleaner vehicle technologies at an unprecedented pace. Much of the literature regarding electric vehicles is centred around charging vehicle infrastructure and levels of market penetration. Consequently, there is an opportunity to explore energy consumption characteristics and produce estimates of energy demands in urban areas. This study employs an agent-based model of vehicle activity to quantify electric energy consumption through the simulation of a heterogeneous fleet of electric vehicles within an urban street network under several experimental conditions.

KEYWORDS: Agent-Based Model, Traffic Simulator, Electric Vehicles, Cities, Public Policy

Introduction

Transport is one of the most significant contributors to greenhouse gas emissions (“Sources of Greenhouse Gas Emissions | US EPA,” n.d.), and the use of road vehicles accounts for nearly 75% of transport-related emissions (“Tracking Transport 2021 – Analysis - IEA,” n.d.). Therefore, electric vehicles (EVs) are commonly presented as a viable alternative, as they can increase fuel efficiency and reduce the impacts of private transport on the environment. The sales of EVs globally increased to 3 million in 2020, a 40% increase from 2019 (“Electric Vehicles – Analysis - IEA,” n.d.). While all vehicle manufacturing companies have started building and testing EVs for the commercial market, there is a limited understanding of the level of energy consumption EVs will require (Sierzchula, Bakker, Maat, & Van Wee, 2012). Understanding the energy consumption of electric vehicles, and, therefore, energy demand is of fundamental importance for policymaking, the development of suitable infrastructure, and climate change, as heightened electricity demand could counteract the benefits of EVs compared to their counterpart ICEVs if this is too high.

The aim of this study is to quantify the relationship between vehicle density and speed limit adherence, and its subsequent impact on electricity consumption (the amount of electricity required by

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the vehicles to complete their drive cycle) within an urban environment. This aim is achieved by employing an agent-based model that has previously been utilised in a similar domain (Olmez, Douglas-Mann, et al., 2021). An energy calculation program is developed, and then applied to an agent-based model previously developed by (Olmez, Sargoni, et al., 2021). This energy calculation program allows energy input and output to be quantified and subsequently explored.

Background

A traffic system is characterised by multiple individual actors (i.e., drivers) and a street network governed by rules. These rules are commonly indicated by features such as traffic lights and posted speed limits. As a traffic system consists of individual-level components, it is well-suited to being studied using individual-based modelling methods. Individual-based modelling refers to simulation models that treat individual entities as unique and discrete components with at least one property (for example, age, height, or name) (Huston, DeAngelis, & Post, 1988). In this study, vehicles are treated as individual heterogeneous entities with properties and rules, while the urban street network is the environment within which these entities (vehicles) are observed.

Several studies within the field of electric vehicle research have employed agent-based models. An agent-based model that measured consumer needs and decision strategies by policymakers to shift from ICEVs to EVs was developed by (Kangur, Jager, Verbrugge, & Bockarjova, 2017). The study demonstrated that effective policy requires a long-lasting implementation of a combination of monetary, structural, and informational measures. Similarly, (Eppstein, Grover, Marshall, & Rizzo, 2011) developed a spatially explicit agent-based vehicle consumer choice model which identified factors that can impact the uptake of PHEVs. The study found that providing consumers with ready estimates of expected lifetime fuel costs associated with other vehicle types, including the rise of petrol costs, can generate preferences for purchasing EV/PHEVs over ICEVs.

As the limited literature suggests, the modelling of EVs is a relatively novel research area. Previous studies have focused on a limited range of issues such as market penetration and charging infrastructure. Therefore, there is an opportunity to develop forecasts of electric energy demand in urban street networks. These forecasts are of critical importance as increased levels of demand for electricity, and the subsequent increases in prices, will influence the uptake of EVs.

Model Description

The agent-based model used within this research is the 3D Urban Traffic Simulator developed in Unity by (Olmez, Sargoni, et al., 2021). The model simulates hypothetical vehicle drive cycle scenarios in a three-dimensional urban environment. In the model, heterogeneous autonomous vehicle agents are assigned granular features including mass, velocity, and traction control. The road network, to which the vehicles are constrained, is designed around a built-up environment that has the characteristics of a dense urban street network, with varying speed limits and intersection rules adopted from the UK Speed Limits (Department for Transport, 2006).

Table 1 Model entities and parameter values (Olmez, Douglas-Mann, et al., 2021)

Entity	Parameter	Values
Vehicles	Mass	[X, Y] (kg)

	Top speed	[30, 45] (mph), [48, 72] (km/h)
	Ray-cast length	[1, 10] (m)
Environment	Number of vehicles	[1, 500]
	Speed adherence	[0, N]
	Roads	1295
	Intersections	354

The model has two entities: the vehicle agents and model environment in which these agents are based. The vehicle parameters (**Table 1**) are:

- The vehicle mass parameter, the value of which is drawn from a random uniform distribution between X and Y kilograms (inclusive); the model distributes vehicles arbitrarily across the environment with varying weights.
- The top speed measure is between 30 and 45mph (48, 72 km/h), and is only applied to the vehicles that do not adhere to speed limits. This measure is applied only if speed adherence is ≥ 1 (source (Balendra, 2020)).
- The ray-cast length parameter can be between 1 to 10 for each vehicle. This variable assigns a distance between two vehicles in meters.

The environment specific parameters (**Table 1**) are:

- The number of vehicles generated in the model, N; this can be between 1 and 500.
- The speed adherence variable can be between $0 \leq x \leq N$. This quantifies the proportion of vehicles which will not adhere to the speed limits applied to the road which they are driving on.
- The urban road network consists of 1295 roads that vehicles drive on and 354 intersections. The road network has been designed to depict a small urban town. For context, Morley, UK, has 1526 roads similar to the urban street network of 1295.

Results

In this study, nine computationally inexpensive experiments were designed and conducted. The independent variables modelled are the density of the vehicle fleet and adherence to speed limits. The experiments, as outlined in **Table 2**, allow energy consumptions to be calculated in alternative environmental and behavioural scenarios. The data generated represent levels of energy consumption in the different scenarios and are explored using visualisations.

Table 2 Experiment conditions (V = number of vehicles, NA = number of vehicles not adhering to speed limits).

Variable	Low adherence	Medium adherence	High adherence
Low vehicle fleet density	Experiment condition 1: 10 V, 10 NA	Experiment condition 2: 10 V, 5 NA	Experiment condition 3: 10 V, 0 NA
Medium vehicle fleet density	Experiment condition 4: 50 V, 50 NA	Experiment condition 5: 50 V, 25 NA	Experiment condition 6: 50 V, 0 NA
High vehicle fleet density	Experiment condition 7: 100 V, 100 NA	Experiment condition 8: 100 V, 50 NA	Experiment condition 9: 100 V, 0 NA

Figure 1 Cumulative energy consumed for each experiment condition

Figure 2 The vehicle speeds for each of the nine experiment conditions

In the experiment conditions in which the entire vehicle fleet did not adhere to speed limits (1, 4, and 7), the levels of energy consumption are highest, regardless of vehicle fleet density (**Figure 1**). However, as the density of the vehicle fleet increased, there is less variability of speed as levels of congestion are higher (**Figure 2**), experiment conditions 4 and 7. Conversely, in high adherence scenarios in which all vehicles adhered to the local and fixed speed limits, levels of energy consumption were similar, regardless of density. These

preliminary results illustrate that vehicle fleet density and speed limit adherence have a profound impact on levels energy of consumption in urban street networks.

Conclusion

This research demonstrates the applicability of agent-based modelling in quantifying energy demand from vehicles in an urban street network. Preliminary results evidence that the number of vehicles and the behaviour of drivers (with regards to speed) impacts the energy consumption of EV/PHEVs. Levels of energy consumption are highest when vehicles are prone to breaking local and fixed speed limits, with levels reaching a maximum of 16 kWh. Energy consumption is lowest in experiment conditions 3, 6, and 9 (**Figure 1**) when vehicles comply with speed limits. As the density of the vehicle fleet increases, the mean vehicle speed reduces; however, the mean levels of energy consumption remain similar. This may occur as increases in the density of the vehicle fleet on the road network result in congestion and, consequently, vehicles travel more slowly. In contrast, the outliers for the experiment conditions 4, 5, 7, and 8 (**Figure 1**), indicate that when the vehicle fleet density is 50, more instances of higher energy consumption exist (12-16kWh) when compared to a vehicle fleet density of 100 (10-12kWh). Thus, as the density of the vehicle fleet increases and adherence to speed limits increases, the levels of energy consumption levels in urban environments decrease.

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Biographies

Sedar Olmez is a PhD student at The Alan Turing Institute and in the School of Geography at the University of Leeds. He is interested in the application of novel deep reinforcement learning frameworks to agent-based models to explore complex adaptive behaviours in response to unbeknown stimuli.

Annabel Whipp is a PhD Student at the School of Geography in the University of Leeds. Her PhD investigates the development of estimates of the size of the ambient population within urban areas and explores their use within crime studies.

Ellie Marfleet is a PhD student at the School of Geography in the University of Leeds. Her research investigates alternate futuristic scenarios concerning the integration of autonomous mobility services to urban areas.

Alison Heppenstall is Professor of Geocomputation with extensive experience in building individual-level models, particularly agent-based and microsimulation models. Her current research is focused on developing and adapting ML and individual-level approaches to understanding the relationship between health and sustainability.

Jason Thompson (B.Sc(Hons), M.Psych(Clinical), PhD(Medicine)) is an Associate Professor at the University of Melbourne's Transport, Health and Urban Design Research Laboratory. His work focuses on the translation of research into practice across the areas of urban design, transportation safety, public health, post-injury rehabilitation, and health system design.

Keiran Suchak is a PhD Student in the School of Geography, based at the Leeds Institute for Data Analytics. Having studied a wide variety of subjects during his education, he has developed an interest in modelling and analysing social systems. His PhD, therefore, focuses on the development of new methods for the simulation of pedestrian motion in urban settings at close to real-time and is partnered with Leeds City Council.

Rajith Vidanaarachchi currently works at the University of Melbourne's Transport, Health and Urban Design Research Lab. In 2021 he completed his PhD titled "Pattern Recognition for Complex Heterogeneous Time-Series Data: An Analysis of Microbial Community Dynamics". He is also a member of the Associate Fellow of the Higher Education Academy.